

COMPARISON OF EFFICACY OF INTRAVENOUS TRAMADOL AND INTRAVENOUS DEXMEDETOMIDINE ON POST-SPINAL ANAESTHESIA SHIVERING IN CAESAREAN SECTION

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Abstract

Postanaesthetic shivering is a usual manifestation after neuraxial anesthesia. Tramadol and Meperidine are the commonly employed agents to abort shivering but unfortunately, these agents are associated with significant nausea and vomiting thus adding to morbidity. The objective of this study was to compare the efficacy profile of tramadol and dexmedetomidine in hampering post spinal shivering in obstetric patients.

Study Design:

Quasi-Experimental Study

Methods:

A total of 120 patients who have undergone elective cesarean section and exhibited post spinal shivering enrolled in the study with uniform distribution in two groups Group T (Tramadol) and group D (Dexmedetomidine). The favorable response, time to termination of shivering, and adverse effects were recorded with subsequent analysis with independent sample t-test and Chi-square test.

Results: A total of (120) female patients underwent elective cesarean section with a mean age of 23±13.00 (18 - 35 years) enrolled in the study. The time to terminate shivering with dexmedetomidine was (172.12 ± 14.26 seconds) whereas tramadol was (278.06 ± 23.17 seconds) (p-value < 0.001). The overall incidence of shivering recurrence was recorded in Group D to be 3(5%) and 10(16.66%) in Group T (p-value 0.03) respectively with a greater propensity of nausea and vomiting with tramadol and moderate sedation with dexmedetomidine.

Conclusion:

Dexmedetomidine exhibited a favorable shivering control profile without notable adverse effects.

INTRODUCTION

Involuntary and persistent recurrent skeletal muscle activity is termed as shivering with 40%-70% reported incidence after anesthesia.^{1,2} Proposed etiologies for post-spinal shivering are intraoperative loss of heat, raised sympathetic tone, pain, and systemic pyrogenic agents. The thermoregulatory function of the hypothalamus is intact in neuraxial anesthesia however it is responsible for greater heat loss when compared with general anesthesia attributable to the vasodilator phenomenon eventually leading to heat loss, the impaired capability of shivering due to block, and preload with fluid.^{3,4}

Shivering can cause deterioration of patient satisfaction consequently causing pain, raised intraocular and intracranial pressure, misinterpretation of standard monitoring particularly pulse oximetry. All of these result in enhanced consumption of oxygen with an associated rise in carbon dioxide which tends to influence intrapulmonary shunts, cardiac out, and restricted respiratory reserve.^{5,6}

Multiple interventions proposed to date to abolish post-anesthesia shivering. Anti-shivering properties are ascribed to dexmedetomidine which is a centrally acting alpha 2 adrenergic agonist with additional sedative properties which is a desirable effect to enhance patient comfort. Numerous studies support the employment of agents as post-anesthesia anti shivering agent.^{7,8}

Tramadol hydrochloride is designated as an opioid receptor agonist that leads to inhibition of serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine) and norepinephrine reuptake in the spinal cord. Hence promoting 5-hydroxytryptamine liberation responsible for thermoregulation. Tramadol and Meperidine are the commonly employed agents to abort shivering but unfortunately, these agents are associated with significant nausea and vomiting thus adding to morbidity.^{9,10}

The objective of this study was to compare the efficacy profile of tramadol and dexmedetomidine in hampering post spinal shivering in obstetric patients.

Methodology:

This quasi experimental study was conducted at AFH Faisalabad.

The minimum sample size calculated for the study was (120) where the prevalence of post-spinal shivering was 8.15% with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error as reported by Luggaya et al.¹¹ With non-probability consecutive sampling a total of (120) participants were randomly distributed in two uniform groups Group - D (60) and Group T (60).

Pregnant patients with age range 18 - 35 years belonging to American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) Grade I, II undergoing elective cesarean section under spinal anesthesia presenting with post-anesthesia shivering and provided informed written consent were included in the trial. Patients with coagulation disorders, heart rate < 60/min, heart diseases, or allergic to constituents of the study were eliminated from the study. Criteria to establish the superiority of either of the agent was defined to be the ability to abort shivering by one minute.

Random allocation into groups was done via computer-originated number and double-blinding ensured with anonymous labeling of similar 50 ml syringes and opted for the person for drug administration and proforma endorsement who was not part of the study. Standard monitoring for regional block (noninvasive blood pressure, pulse rate, oxygen saturation, temperature) was ensured. The subarachnoid block is given in L2 - L3 or L4 - L5 space with 0.5% bupivacaine. Fluid warming was omitted with a constant temperature of 24°C of the operating zone. Noninvasive blood pressure, pulse rate, oxygen saturation, and axillary temperature were noted at baseline with subsequent records after every 10 minutes upon the advent of shivering. Intravenous dexmedetomidine (0.5 mcg/kg) in the concentration of 1 mcg/ml in Group D and intravenous tramadol (0.5 mg/kg) in the concentration of 1 mg/ml in Group T was given over 10 min, upon the advent of grade III or IV shivering, defined as follows.

Table - 1: Grades of Shivering¹²

Grade 0	No shivering
Grade 1	Piloerection, peripheral vasoconstriction, peripheral cyanosis without other cause, but visible muscle activity
Grade 2	Visible muscle activity confined to one muscle group
Grade 3	Visible muscle activity in more than one muscle group
Grade 4	Gross muscle activity involving the whole body

Onset and recurrence of shivering after subarachnoid block, grade of shivering, termination of shivering along time taken for termination were recorded. Treatment failure is defined to be a failure of cessation after 15 minutes of drug administration. Adverse events

such as nausea, vomiting, itching, decreased heart rate <60 per minute, a decrease of mean arterial blood pressure >20% of baseline, and sedation scores as elaborated below were endorsed.

Table- 2: Modified Ramsay Sedation Score ¹³

Grade 1	Anxious and restless
Grade 2	Cooperative and Oriented
Grade 3	Responds to Commands only
Grade 4	Brisk response to a light glabellar tap or loud noise
Grade 5	Sluggish response to a light glabellar tap or loud noise
Grade 6	No response

Bradycardia and reduced mean arterial pressure were treated if recorded to be 20% below baseline with intravenous atropine and ephedrine

respectively. Injection metoclopramide 10 mg was administered for nausea and vomiting.

Table - 3: Bromage Score for Motor Response ¹⁴

Grade 0	Full flexion of knees and feet
Grade I	Just able to move the knee
Grade II	Able to move feet only
Grade III	Unable to move feet or knee

Data was entered and analyzed by data management software IBM SPSS (version 23.0). Data was interpreted as mean ± SD or percentage by using the Chi-square test and independent samples T-test among groups. A p-value of ≤0.05 was considered significant.

Results:

A total of (120) female patients enrolled in the study with a mean age of 23±13.00 (18 -35 years). The mean weight of the cohort was 75.60±9.24 Kilograms. 74(61.66%) and 46(38.34%) patients were from the American Society of Anesthesiologists status I and II respectively. The

overall incidence of shivering recurrence was recorded in Group D to be 3(5%) and 10(16.66%) in Group T (p-value 0.03). Onset, severity, time to recurrence, and time to cessation of shivering are elucidated in Table - 4.

17(28.33%) patients in Group T complained of nausea and vomiting whereas none of the patients in Group - D had.2(3.33%) patients had bradycardia in Group D whereas none of the patients had hypotension in either of the groups. Maximum sedation score of 2 recorded in Group D patients. Duration of surgery and spinal anesthesia are elaborated in Table - 5.

Table – 4: Comparison of Shivering Parameters

	Group D	Group T	P- value
Onset of Shivering(minutes)	73.30±41.35	72.66±41.64	0.95
Cessation of Shivering(seconds)	172.12 ± 14.26	278.06 ± 23.17	<0.001*
Recurrence of Shivering(minutes)	70.00±17.32	73.75±21.17	0.67
Severity of Shivering	3.92±0.21	3.96±0.19	0.41

Table - 5: Comparison of Surgical and Anesthetic Parameters

	Group D	Group T
Duration of Surgery (minutes)	78.62±30.18	86.40±34.02
Duration of Anesthesia (minutes)	122.90±29.26	133.30±32.36

Discussion:

In this quasi-experimental study, the efficacy of dexmedetomidine was compared with tramadol in the alleviation of post-spinal shivering in parturient undergoing elective cesarean section. In this study, the termination of shivering with tramadol hydrochloride was achieved in 278.06 ± 23.17 seconds whereas this aim was achieved with much less time with dexmedetomidine 172.12 ± 14.26 seconds (p-value < 0.001).

Singla et al employed (50) patients in each group targeted with dexmedetomidine and tramadol for abolishing shivering after neuraxial anesthesia. They concluded that rescue therapy for shivering control was required in two patients in the tramadol group whereas none of the patients were subjected to additional therapy for alleviation of post-spinal shivering in the dexmedetomidine group. Sedation was recorded in the dexmedetomidine group whereas post-operative nausea and vomiting were more prevalent in the tramadol trial group. They concluded dexmedetomidine to be a more suitable agent for post-spinal shivering (p-value < 0.001). These results were consistent with our study.¹⁵

Singh et al conducted a randomized controlled trial to compare dexmedetomidine and tramadol for alleviation of perioperative shivering in transurethral resection of prostate under subarachnoid alleviation. They concluded that treatment was effective in (98.30%) patients of the dexmedetomidine group whereas the success

rate was (86.67%) in the tramadol group. Similarly, recurrence of post-spinal shivering was less in the dexmedetomidine group.¹⁶

Wang et al conducted a meta-analysis in thirteen randomized controlled studies which included 864 patients. They concluded that dexmedetomidine had greater effective control of shivering (p-value = 0.01), less time to abort shivering (p-value < 0.0000), lower recurrence (p-value 0.001), decreased incidence of nausea (p-value < 0.00001), and vomiting (p-value < 0.00001), higher incidence of sedation (p-value 0.005), hypotension (p-value 0.01) and bradycardia (p-value 0.002), compared with tramadol.¹⁷

Limitations attributable to the study were that core body temperature measured via probe mid-esophagus, tympanic membrane, or urinary bladder could not be recorded.¹⁸ However this method could cause discomfort in awake patients undergoing subarachnoid block and being invasive can pose infection.

Conclusion:

Dexmedetomidine exhibited a favorable shivering control profile without notable adverse effects.

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